

**The role of the oral microbiome in the aetiopathogenesis of peri-implantitis:
microbiological, immunological and structural aspects**

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ABSTRACT: This study aimed to develop, validate, and clinically evaluate the relationship between dental implantation and disturbances in the microbiological balance of the oral cavity. The paper summarises the results of microbiological studies aimed at establishing a correlation between the identified changes. For the analysis, a group of 20 patients aged 25–60 years without concomitant somatic diseases was formed, from whom samples were taken for microbiological testing.

The study results revealed significant quantitative shifts in the composition of the microflora. A 3.7-fold decrease in staphylococcus titres was observed compared with those of healthy individuals, a 1.8-fold decrease in green streptococci, a 2.8-fold decrease in *Neisseria*, a 1.7-fold decrease in lactobacilli and a 1.5-fold decrease in *Veillonella*. At the same time, a twofold increase in the concentration of fusobacteria was recorded, and the content of actinomycetes increased 2.4-fold. The total number of bacteroides increased 1.2-fold, including odontogenic bacteroides by 1.3-fold; a twofold increase in the number of fungi of the genus *Candida* was also observed.

This study confirms that an increase in the concentration of pathogenic microorganisms initiates a destructive cascade reaction leading to the development of peri-implantitis. Understanding these mechanisms is of fundamental importance for the development of personalised strategies for the diagnosis and prevention of complications associated with dental implantation.

KEYWORDS: Peri-implantitis; Oral microbiome.

RESUMEN: El objetivo de este estudio fue desarrollar, validar y evaluar clínicamente la relación entre la implantación dental y las alteraciones del equilibrio microbiológico de la cavidad oral. El artículo resume los resultados de estudios microbiológicos dirigidos a establecer una correlación entre los cambios identificados. Para el análisis se constituyó un grupo de 20 pacientes de 25 a 60 años sin enfermedades somáticas concomitantes, de quienes se tomaron muestras para pruebas microbiológicas. Los resultados del estudio revelaron cambios cuantitativos significativos en la

composición de la microflora. Se observó una disminución de 3,7 veces en los títulos de estafilococos en comparación con individuos sanos, una disminución de 1,8 veces en estreptococos verdes, una disminución de 2,8 veces en Neisseria, una disminución de 1,7 veces en lactobacilos y una disminución de 1,5 veces en Veillonella. Al mismo tiempo, se registró un aumento de dos veces en la concentración de fusobacterias y un incremento de 2,4 veces en el contenido de actinomicetos. El número total de bacteroides aumentó 1,2 veces, incluyendo bacteroides odontogénicos en 1,3 veces; también se observó un aumento de dos veces en el número de hongos del género Candida.

Este estudio confirma que el aumento de la concentración de microorganismos patógenos inicia una reacción en cadena destructiva que conduce al desarrollo de la periimplantitis. La comprensión de estos mecanismos es de importancia fundamental para el desarrollo de estrategias personalizadas para el diagnóstico y la prevención de complicaciones asociadas con la implantación dental.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Periimplantitis; microbioma oral.

INTRODUCTION

Dentistry and dental practice now have extensive experience in replacing teeth following treatment using dental implants. Alongside the positive outcomes of implantation, various complications are also observed when performing this procedure. Problems can arise both in the early and late stages following implantation and tooth replacement. The most likely cause of complications around implants is the spread of infection from the mouth to the area where the implant contacts the bone. The microbial composition of the soft tissues surrounding implants is now well understood and includes a variety of aerobic and anaerobic bacteria. The inflammatory process in the tissues around the implants is the main cause of bone destruction and damage in the implant area.

In the modern context, the impact of dental implants on the development of late inflammatory complications following dental implantation is becoming increasingly significant; these complications currently manifest as inflammatory processes within the oral cavity. The literature indicates that disturbances in the oral microbiome are linked to oral hygiene, as well as dental and gum diseases.

The main complications associated with tooth replacement using dental implants today are inflammatory processes near the implants. The onset of inflammation depends on a multitude of factors. A review of the specialist literature strongly supports the microbial theory of the origin of inflammatory complications. The most common

complications of dental implantation are mucositis and peri-implantitis, which occur in the area of the implants. Since mucositis is the so-called initial stage of peri-implantitis development, without compromising bone integrity, our research focused on the study of peri-implantitis.

The microbial composition in cases of peri-implantitis includes a wide range of aerobic and anaerobic bacteria. Microbiological studies have shown that the oral microbiome is severely disrupted in patients with peri-implantitis. The most serious disturbances in the microflora, manifesting as dysbiosis, are observed in patients with severe forms of the disease. Local immune defence factors play a significant role in this context. Thus, the presence of local immunodeficiency always causes changes in the microbial balance of the biocenosis, particularly in the gingival tissues, and leads to increased colonisation by the aforementioned microorganisms. The results of clinical and microbiological studies of patients show that the degree of disturbance in the oral biocenosis is associated with the clinical form of peri-implantitis. It has been established that dysbiotic changes exacerbate the clinical picture of the disease.

Dentists now have extensive experience in restoring patients' teeth using dental implants. Alongside the positive outcomes of implantation, various problems associated with this method can also arise. One such problem is peri-implantitis – a condition affecting the area around the implant. This problem can develop either shortly after or some time following implantation and prosthetic restoration. The most likely cause of peri-implantitis is thought to be an infection spreading from the mouth to the site where the implant meets the bone. The bacteria involved in peri-implantitis are well-known and include many aerobic and anaerobic microorganisms. Inflammation of the tissues around the implant is the main cause of bone destruction and resorption in the area surrounding the implant.

The ability of bacteria to form robust biofilms on virtually any surface, including medical instruments and equipment, presents a serious problem in the field of medicine and dentistry in particular. This is particularly relevant in the context of dental peri-implant infections, which require further investigation.

The exposed surface of the implant is rapidly colonised, resulting in the formation of a biotope of various microorganisms, which can significantly affect the condition of the bone and soft tissues surrounding the implant. Deterioration in oral hygiene and local resistance factors can lead to the development of mucositis, peri-implantitis and bone resorption.

When investigating the relationship between the occurrence of inflammatory reactions around implants and the state of the oral microbiome, it is important to focus on the

bacterial composition of mixed saliva and dental plaque in the area of the implants themselves. The biotope, obtained from mixed saliva, is formed from the diverse niches present in the oral cavity, and reflects the overall microbiome of this area.

The aim of the study is to develop a comprehensive, etiologically grounded treatment protocol for dental peri-implantitis based on the correction of the oral microbiome.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted at the Department of Prosthodontics as a research program aimed at the development and clinical validation of quantitative and qualitative change microbioma of mouth to prevent cases of periimplantitis .

As part of this study, a comprehensive clinical and laboratory investigation was conducted on a group of 24 patients, systematically selected during consultation visits. All patients had a clinically and radiographically confirmed diagnosis of peri-implantitis. We included patients in the study with resorption in the implant neck region not exceeding 5 mm. All participants were in satisfactory general somatic health, had no decompensated chronic diseases, and presented no absolute contraindications to implant therapy.

To validate the results, a control group of 18 patients with stable implants and no signs of peri-implantitis was formed. The assessment of dental status was carried out following a thorough review of patients' complaints, medical history, and a detailed examination of the maxillofacial region. During the examination, particular attention was paid to the condition of the teeth and dental arches, the mucous membrane of the oral cavity, the functionality of the temporomandibular joint, and the characteristics of the occlusion.

The clinical diagnosis for each patient included a detailed analysis of oral hygiene, with a focus on assessing the implant site. An assessment was carried out of the degree of gingival bleeding, which is an important indicator of inflammatory processes. The degree of gingival recession was also measured, from the 'neck' of the implant to the gingival margin, using specific criteria for assessing the degree of recession, which ranged from 0 to 5 points.

These metrics provided objective data on the condition of the tissues surrounding the implants and enabled an assessment of their resistance to pathological changes. To take accurate measurements of the depth of peri-implant pockets, as well as to determine the presence of subgingival deposits on the surface of the implants, a periodontal graduated probe with a minimum scale division of 1 mm was used. Pocket depth measurements were taken from four different sides: distal, medial, vestibular and oral.

The greatest recorded pocket depth among those measured provided the final indicator within the study, indicating maximum tissue penetration and potential risk areas for inflammatory processes in the peri-implant region.

All patients with peri-implantitis underwent radiographic examination. For a general assessment of the condition of the jaws, teeth and implants, cone-beam computed tomography was performed. To obtain a more accurate image of the implant and the condition of the surrounding bone tissue, including the depth of the bone pocket, intraoral radiographs were taken, which were performed using a positioning device. This helped to avoid artifacts and distortions in the radiographic image.

RESULTS

During the initial examination at the clinic, patients reported complaints of intermittent pain in the gingival tissues around the implants, predominantly during or after eating. Physical examination revealed a significant accumulation of soft and hard dental plaque on the prosthetic superstructures placed on the implants. The mean Greene–Vermillion index was 1.8 ± 0.25 ; 100% of patients exhibited gingival bleeding, and the mean SBI index was 2.50 in the implant area, with 50% of the subjects, bleeding occurred immediately after running the tip of the probe along the sulcus wall. 76.5% patients suffered from halitosis. Only 16.7% of patients underwent professional dental hygiene twice a year, whilst the majority (66.7%) underwent this procedure only once a year, which is significantly below the recommended standards. Fourteen patients (58.3%) had a history of chronic periodontitis.

On palpation, a small amount of exudate was detected in the peri-implant tissues. Peri-implant pockets with a depth of 2.53 ± 0.95 mm were diagnosed, indicating serious compromise of the gingival margin integrity around the implants.

Radiographic findings showed bone resorption of 2–4 mm in the cervical region of the implants, confirming the clinical findings. Analysis of the microbial load prior to treatment revealed significant deviations from the norm, necessary for maintaining a healthy oral microbiome.

An analysis of the microbiological status of the study participants revealed a correlation between changes in the oral microflora and the clinical form of peri-implantitis. Thus, in mild forms of peri-implantitis, the oral microflora comprised all the microbes found

in healthy individuals. The frequency of their detection differed little from the norm, and any minor changes were random (aerobic and anaerobic Gram-positive and Gram-negative microbes). Similar results were obtained in the quantitative analysis of oral microbes, although for some groups of bacteria a difference was observed, manifested as a decrease in CFU/ml for *Streptococcus salivarius* (from 7.4 to 5.6), peptococci (from 7.0 to 5.8) and, conversely, an increase in fusobacteria from 2.6 to 5.4 and 'odontogenic' bacteroides from 3.2 to 4.4 ($p < 0.05$).

In cases of moderate peri-implantitis, the proportion of most species and groups comprising the normal oral flora was reduced: green streptococci from 100.0% to 56% ($p < 0.01$), staphylococci from 90.0% to 53.7% ($p < 0.01$), diphtheroids from 55.0% to 5.7% ($p < 0.01$), and *Neisseria* from 90.0% to 34.2% ($p < 0.01$). There was a less significant ($p > 0.05$) decrease in the number of pneumococci (from 25.0% to 11.4%) and lactobacilli (from 80.0% to 53.5%). Whilst there was a slight decrease in the total number of bacteroids to 76.2%, their species composition changed markedly: whereas *Pr. melaninogenicus* and other bacteroides predominated in healthy subjects and those with mild disease, in cases of moderate severity their frequency of isolation decreased sharply, whilst the proportion of odontogenic anaerobes increased from 10.0% to 75.3% ($p < 0.05$). An increase in the frequency of isolation of fungi of the genus *Candida* from 25.0% to 50.0% was also noted ($p < 0.05$).

In patients with severe forms of peri-implantitis, *Haemophilus*, pneumococci and other cocci were absent; the isolation rates of non-green streptococci, staphylococci, diphtheroids, *Neisseria* and *Veillonella* were significantly lower ($p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$). At the same time, the frequency of detection of fungi of the genus *Candida* increased (from 15 to 50.0%) and of odontogenic bacteroids (from 16 to 80.3%). The number of green streptococci was 2.3 times lower than in healthy individuals, staphylococci 4.3 times lower, *Neisseria* 3.6 times lower, lactobacilli 2.6 times lower, and *Veillonella* 2 times lower. At the same time, the concentration of fusobacteria increased twofold, and that of actinomycetes by 3.2 times. The total number of bacteroids increased 1.6-fold, including odontogenic bacteroids, which increased 1.7-fold. Trichomonads, spirochetes and spirilla were detected in 5 (16.6%) patients (the latter in only 6.6%).

According to some researchers (Ivanov V. S., 2001; Tsepov L. M., 2001), the main symptom of peri-implantitis and the onset of the inflammatory process is the implant-gingival pocket, the study of whose biocenosis is of interest. When the pocket depth was no more than 4 mm, in most cases a slightly lower frequency of aerobic and microaerophilic flora was observed than in healthy subjects ($p < 0.05$). Species such as

pneumococci and diphtheroids were not detected. In the anaerobic fraction of the microflora, significant changes were observed only in the 'mutans' streptococci group (90% and 64%, $p < 0.05$) and peptostreptococci (95% and 60%, $p < 0.05$). The concentration of the identified microorganisms remained virtually unchanged, although the CFU/ml of peptostreptococci in patients in this group decreased from 6.2 (normal) to 4.4. The change in the spectrum of microorganisms isolated from periodontal pockets deeper than 6 mm was more pronounced and statistically significant (90.0% and 40.0%, $p < 0.01$, and 95% and 28.5%, $p < 0.01$). In cases of marked gingival bleeding, most members of the normal microflora were isolated less frequently: *Streptococcus salivarius* in 80.0% and 22.8% ($p < 0.01$), *Staphylococcus* in 50.0% and 17.0% ($p < 0.05$), *Lactobacilli* – in 25.0% and 5.7% ($p < 0.05$). The number of these microorganisms decreased by a factor of 1.1–1.8; the difference in CFU/ml was particularly marked for peptostreptococci—6.2 in healthy subjects and 3.4 in patients. The frequency of detection of bacteroides decreased slightly (from 90.0% to 82.8%), but the proportion of 'odontogenic' bacteroides rose sharply from 2.8% to 61.8% ($p < 0.05$). Noteworthy is the doubling of the isolation rate of fungi of the genus *Candida* (from 15.0% to 31.0%). The frequency of detection of actinomycetes increased in the presence of serous-purulent exudate (from 10.0% to 14.3%); the quantitative indicator of this microorganism increased 3.2-fold – from 1.7 to 5.5 CFU/ml – in cases of purulent discharge.

DISCUSSION

Our research findings indicate that as the inflammatory-destructive process progresses and its clinical manifestations intensify, significant changes occur in the microbiological profile of patients with peri-implantitis. This applies to the biocenosis of the periodontal pocket: some bacteria typical of healthy tissue (*Neisseria*, pneumococci, other cocci) disappear, and the number of most obligate and facultative anaerobes characteristic of this biotope (*Veillonella*, *Peptostreptococcus*, *Lactobacilli*, green and non-green streptococci). 'Odontogenic' bacteroides, fungi of the genus *Candida*, and to a lesser extent (due to higher concentrations) actinomycetes and fusobacteria begin to play a significant role. In severe forms of peri-implantitis, periodontal pockets also harbour the difficult-to-identify *A. actinomycetemcomitans*, as well as opportunistic aerobic species such as *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus*.

Protozoa are also likely to play a significant role in the development of a more severe course of the disease, as their detection in native swabs becomes increasingly common as the disease progresses from mild to more severe forms.

Analysis of the total number of microorganisms in the oral cavity (including both 'normal flora' and opportunistic pathogens) revealed that in the control group and in patients with mild peri-implantitis, 10–9 species and groups of microorganisms were predominantly observed. In the control group, such results were observed in 90% of those examined, and in patients with mild peri-implantitis, in 96%. In cases of moderate and severe disease, a reduction in the number of microorganisms was observed. In the first case, 8–6 species were isolated from the oral cavity in 82.7% of patients, whilst in the second, the number of associated species in all patients did not exceed 7 (23.3%), but the majority comprised patients in whom 6 (30.0%) and 5 (46.6%) species were identified. Conducting a similar analysis using material from the implant-gingival sulcus revealed that the total number of associated species was significantly lower here. In the microbiocenosis of this biotope, the number of associated species was: in healthy subjects – 7–6 (80.0%); in patients with mild peri-implantitis – 6–3 (80.0%); moderate and severe – 5–3 (74.3%) and 4–2 (93.4%), respectively.

Furthermore, in implant-gingival sulci deeper than 6 mm and in severe cases of the disease, a clear pattern emerges: 'odontogenic' bacteria predominate, having been detected in 80.0% of patients in the second group and 86.0% of patients in the third group. It should be noted that *Acinobacillus actinomycetemcomitans* was detected only in cases of abscess formation and the presence of purulent exudate, occurring in 13.3% of cases; it was the sole representative of periodontopathogenic flora present in high titres, and in two cases was isolated in association with *Por. gingivalis*.

Analysis of samples from the oral cavity and implant-gingival sulci revealed that in healthy individuals and in patients in the first group, the microflora is quite diverse and consists of 9–10 or more species. With the development of peri-implantitis, the number of species in the biocenosis decreases to 8–6 in moderate cases and to 7–8 in severe cases of peri-implantitis. An even greater 'depletion' occurs in the implant-gingival sulci: whilst 7–6 species (groups) of bacteria were isolated in healthy subjects, this figure was 5–3 in patients with moderate disease and no more than 4–2 species in those with severe disease. In the oral cavity and in the implant-gingival sulci of patients with moderate and severe peri-implantitis, one or two representatives of this group were dominant. This trend is particularly pronounced in the implant-gingival sulci.

According to some researchers (Ushakov R. V., 1998; Rabinovich I. M., 2002), changes in the abundance and composition of microorganisms may, over time, develop into a disease in their own right and act as an additional factor in the development of chronic inflammatory diseases of the mouth. As our research results have shown, the degree of disturbance in the biocenosis may vary among patients with peri-implantitis.

We classified patients according to the severity of dysbiosis based on the calculation of the dysbiosis index (DI).

Thus, the control group exhibited a normal state of the microflora (DI 0.8–0.7). A mild dysbiotic shift (DI 0.7–0.6) was observed in patients with a low degree of PII. Grade I dysbiosis (DI 0.6–0.4) was diagnosed in cases of moderate PII. Grade II dysbiosis (DI 0.06 or less) corresponded to severe peri-implantitis. This classification is provisional and does not account for all possible quantitative changes. Nevertheless, it helps to improve the approach to diagnosis and comprehensive treatment of the disease.

CONCLUSION

Microbiological studies have thus shown that the oral microbiome is significantly disrupted in patients with peri-implantitis. The most pronounced disturbances in the microflora, characterised by dysbiosis, are observed in patients with severe forms of the disease. The results of clinical and microbiological studies of patients indicate that the extent of disturbances in the oral microbiota is associated with the clinical form of peri-implantitis. It was also established that dysbiotic changes exacerbate the clinical presentation of the disease.

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